

INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT MULCHES AND DRIP IRRIGATION LEVELS ON GROWTH AND SEED YIELD OF ONION
CV. AKOLA SAFEDB. J. Patle¹, S. M. Ghawade², P. K. Nagre³, D. M. Panchbhai⁴, M. M. Deshmukh⁵, R. N. Katkar⁶,

Department of Horticulture,

Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra-444104, India.

badaljip@gmail.com

(MS Received: 12.07.2023; MS Revised: 23.08.2023; MS Accepted: 23.08.2023)

MS 3093

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE)

Abstract

A field experiments were conducted during the rabi season of 2017-18 at Chilli and Vegetable Research Unit, Dr. PDKV, Akola, to study the Influence of different mulches and drip irrigation levels on growth and seed yield of onion CV. Akola safed. The treatments consisted of factorial combinations of three levels of mulches (organic mulch, silver black polyethylene mulch and no mulch) and three levels of irrigation requirement (100 % IWR, 90 % IWR and 80 % IWR) laid out in Strip Plot Design with three replications. Results of the experiment revealed that, height of plant (cm), height of primary and secondary flower stalk (cm), number of primary and secondary umbels per plant, diameter of primary and secondary umbel (cm), number of seeds per primary and secondary umbels, seed yield per plant (g) and seed yield per hectare (q) were recorded maximum due to the application of polyethylene mulch (M₂) and supply of 100 % irrigation water requirement (I₁) through drip irrigation. Whereas, due to the combined application of polyethylene mulch along with 100 % irrigation water (M₂I₁) height of plant (cm), height of primary and secondary umbels (cm), diameter of primary and secondary umbel (cm), number of seeds per primary and secondary umbels, seed yield per plant (g) and seed yield per hectare (q) were recorded significantly maximum as against rest of the treatment combinations.

Key words: Polyethylene mulch, Drip irrigation, Seed yield, Onion, plant growth

Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is the important vegetable crop belongs to *Alliaceae* family. It is a native of Asia and perhaps introduced from Palestine to India. It is important bulbous crop used widely both as spice and vegetable. Onion used as both mature and immature bulb stages as vegetable. Its cultivation is expanding owing to great demand in both domestic consumption as well as for export purpose. Nutritionally, it contains vitamins B and C with traces of iron and calcium, it is low in calories and high in ascorbic acid. It has both glucose (reducing sugar) and sucrose (non-reducing sugar). It also contains an essential volatile oil chiefly constituting "Allyl-propyl-disulphide" which imparts characteristic pungency as reported by Simandi *et al.* (2000). India rank first in area of 1654 thousand hectares, second in production of 26916 thousand metric tonnes and productivity of 16.27 metric tonnes per hectares of onion in the world (Anon, 2022). Maharashtra stands first in total production of onion in the country. Onion is cultivated throughout the India, but the most important onion producing states in India are Maharashtra, Karnataka, Orissa, Uttar Pradesh, Gujrat, Andhra Pradesh and Tamilnadu. In Maharashtra, leading onion producing districts are Pune, Satara, Ahmednager, Solapur, Aurangabad, Beed, Latur, Osmanabad, Jalgoan, Nandurbar, Buldhana, Dhulia and Nashik. The area covered by onion cultivation in Maharashtra is 703.80 thousand hectares with a total production of 10476.46 thousand metric tonnes and average productivity of 14.89 metric tonnes per hectares (Anon, 2022). Onion being extensively cultivated crop, there is a heavy demand for fresh seeds every year. Good quality seed act as a catalyst for realizing the potential of other inputs in agriculture. Without good seed, the investment on water, fertilizers, pesticide and other inputs will not pay the desired dividends. Therefore, seed is considered to be one of the most crucial inputs in agriculture. The thrust for increase in agricultural productivity, which comes from the development of new varieties, could be realized only by making available sufficient quantity of good seed to the farming community at an affordable price at the right time. In case of onion, viability of seed is less than 12 months under ambient conditions. Therefore, every year it is highly essential to produce fresh seed as per requirement.

The annual seed production of the country is about 9600 tonnes. In which 8 per cent seed production of onion is produced from public sector organisation in the country, 9 per cent by the private seed companies and 13 per cent by private traders. Rest of the 70 per cent seed production is produced by the farmers from their own saved seed. Thus, there is the big gap between improved varieties seed and requirement of the country. To bridge this gap, the holistic planning is needed for the production of breeder, foundation, certified and

truthful onion seed of recommended varieties for different regions. At present, Jalana district of Maharashtra and few pockets of Telangana and Gujarat are the only area, wherefrom seed production of onion has been considered for domestic requirement of the country. In Maharashtra, seed production is done only in traditional ways, where the seed yield is 7 to 8 quintal per hectare. While, the Saurashtra region of Gujrat yields 10 to 12 quintals per hectare (Gupta and Sharma, 2014).

Incorporation of advanced technology *i.e.*, use of polyethylene mulch, drip irrigation system, fertigation *etc.*, for increasing the quality seed production of onion form a strong need of present era. Among the various inputs applied to onion, irrigation water is crucial one. Shortage of irrigation water at critical stages of onion seed crop reduces seed yield significantly. Appropriate use of irrigation system with higher water use efficiency might further elevate the seed productivity. Several researchers reported that, higher crop yields can be obtained through drip irrigation along with considerable saving in irrigation water (Sankar *et al.*, 2015).

Onion crop is very sensitive to irrigation, since it has got relatively shallow root zone and requires more frequent irrigation. The low yield of such a valued crop could also be attributed to surface irrigation method predominantly adopted by farmers. Drip irrigation with limited water application seems to be a better alternative to improve onion seed production as well as quality. Among various factors responsible for achieving higher seed yield, the irrigation quantity and method of irrigation plays a vital role in enhancing the growth and productivity of onion. The water requirement for onion seed production was reduced to the extent of 39.88 per cent, when irrigation is applied by drip as compared to conventional surface methods (Dingre *et al.*, 2012).

Among the several water management strategies, mulching was identified as a most efficient practice for increasing the water use efficiency (WUE). The polyethylene sheets too provides several benefits such as conservation of moisture, optimizing the temperature at root zone and minimizing weed flora as well as mist insect at soil surface. Furthermore, it helps in the maintenance of the field capacity by checking the evapotranspiration losses by giving irrigation every alternate day in the present experiment. Considering all above facts and need of this study is to improve the seed production of onion. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to study the 'influence of different mulches and drip irrigation levels on growth and seed yield of onion'.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out during *rabi* season of 2017-18 at Chilli and Vegetable Research Unit, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi

Vidyapeeth, Akola. The experiment was laid out in Strip Plot Design with three replications. There were two factors, the first being mulching of field with three levels *i.e.*, organic mulch (M_1), silver on black polyethylene mulch (M_2) and no mulch (M_3). The second factor was drip irrigation levels viz. 100 % (I_1), 90 % (I_2), and 80 % (I_3) irrigation water requirement on the basis of delay pan evaporation to onion crop. The crop was irrigated at every alternate day as per the irrigation levels. In all there were nine treatment combinations. The bulbs were planted in broad bed furrow (BBF) of 100 cm width and bulbs were planted at the spacing of 60 X 45 cm. Each bed consists of two drip line. All the required cultural practices such as irrigation, weeding, etc. were given uniformly and when necessary. The height of onion plant was measured from ground level to the tip of the longest leaf with the help of meter scale in centimeter (cm), the height of primary and secondary flower stock was measured from ground level to the top of the seed head with the help of meter scale in centimeter (cm), the number of primary and secondary umbels per plant were counted initially at emergence of umbels and at harvest, the diameter of primary and secondary umbels was measured with the help of Varner's caliper in centimeter at full bloom stage, the number of seed per primary and secondary umbels are harvested and counted separately, the average seed yield per plant (g) and per hectare (q) was calculate as per the treatments. The data obtained on various parameters was statistically analyzed as per the methods suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1967).

Results and Discussion

Effect of different mulches on growth and seed yield parameter

The data presented in Table 1 revealed that, the different mulches treatments on plant height, height of primary and secondary flower stalk, number of primary and secondary umbel per plant, diameter of primary and secondary umbel, number of seed per primary and secondary umbel, seed yield per plant and seed yield per hectare were found to be significant, during the experiments.

In the experimentation, the application of polyethylene mulch (M_2) to onion crop depicted that, significantly maximum plant height, height of primary and secondary flower stalk, number of primary and secondary umbel per plant, diameter of primary and secondary umbel, number of seed per primary and secondary umbel, seed yield per plant and seed yield per hectare and it were followed by the treatment organic mulch (M_1). However, it were found minimum in the treatment no mulch (M_3) was applied.

It might be due to the availability of optimum growing conditions provided through conservation of adequate soil moisture, efficient use of nutrients due to application of silver on black polyethylene mulch throughout the growing period of onion plant, ultimately resulting in vigorous growth, higher flowering and seed set and thereby maximum number of flower stalk, number of seeds per umbels, seed yield per plant are resulted. Results of the present investigation are in close agreement with the findings of Anisuzzaman *et al.*, (2009) in onion seed production, Gupta *et al.*, (2013) in onion bulb production, Parmar *et al.*, (2013) in Water melon, Rubel *et al.*, (2014) in onion seed production, and Mukulkumar *et al.*, (2018) in Turmeric.

Effect of drip irrigation levels on growth and seed yield parameter

The data presented in Table 1 revealed that, the different drip irrigation treatments on plant height, height of primary and secondary flower stalk, number of primary and secondary umbel per plant, diameter of primary and secondary umbel, number of seed per primary and secondary umbel, seed yield per plant and seed yield per hectare were found to be significant, during the experiments.

In the experimentation, the supplied of 100% irrigation water requirement through drip (I_1) to onion crop depicted that, significantly the maximum plant height, height of primary and secondary flower stalk, number of primary and secondary umbel per plant, diameter of primary and secondary umbel, number of seed per primary and secondary umbel, seed yield per plant and seed yield per

hectare. Whereas, the number of seeds per primary and secondary umbel, seed yield per plant and seed yield per hectare at par with 90% irrigation water requirement through drip (I_1). However, it was found minimum in the treatment supplied of 80 % irrigation water requirement (I_3) through drip irrigation to the onion crop.

Application of irrigation water at optimum level to onion crop might help to produce large size of umbels, its early emergence and large resources available for seed setting and development. Further, water play vital role in photosynthesis, translocation of photosynthates and activation of various enzymes in plant, ultimately produced large number of seeds per umbels, thus it naturally reflects in maximum seed yield per plant. The results of present investigation are in close agreement with the findings of Dingre *et al.*, (2012), Sankar *et al.*, (2015) in onion seed production, Enchalew *et al.*, (2016) in onion bulb production and Gupta *et al.*, (2017) in Garlic.

Interaction effect of different mulches and drip irrigation levels on growth and yield parameters

The data presented in Table 2 exhibited that, an interaction effects due to different mulches and irrigation levels on plant height, height of primary and secondary flower stalk, diameter of primary and secondary umbel, number of seed per primary and secondary umbel, seed yield per plant and seed yield per hectare were found to be statistically significant. Whereas, the interaction effect of different mulches and drip irrigation levels in respect to number of primary and secondary umbel per plant were found to be non- significant results.

During the study, an application of polyethylene mulch along with 100 % irrigation water requirement to the onion crop (M_2I_1) reflected significantly the maximum plant height, height of primary and secondary flower stalk, diameter of primary and secondary umbel, number of seed per primary and secondary umbel, seed yield per plant and seed yield per hectare and it was at par results with polyethylene mulch with 90% irrigation water requirement (M_2I_2). However, no mulch application along with 80 % irrigation water requirement (M_3I_3) noticed minimum plant height, height of primary and secondary flower stalk, diameter of primary and secondary umbel, number of seed per primary and secondary umbel, seed yield per plant and seed yield per hectare.

The combined effect of silver black polyethylene mulch and higher irrigation levels expressed as maximum number of seeds and seed yield per plant and per hectare, since such treatment provide more moisture conservation, better utilization of nutrients, higher rates of photosynthesis and excess dry matter accumulation, which finally lead to vigorous plant growth and best seed yield of onion than rest of treatment combinations. These findings are in close agreement with the results obtained Alenazi *et al.*, (2015) in Muskmelon, Patle *et al.*, (2018) in Cauliflower and Shahi *et al.*, (2019) in Broccoli.

Conclusion

It is inferred from the above result that, the growth and seed yield of onion in general *i.e.* plant height (cm), height of primary and secondary flower stalk (cm), diameter of primary and secondary umbel (cm), number of seed per primary and secondary umbel, seed yield per plant (g) and seed yield per hectare (q) had exhibited significantly maximum due to the application of polyethylene mulch along with replenishment of 100 % irrigation water requirement (M_2I_1) as compared to rest of the treatments and it was at par with the treatment polyethylene mulch along with replenishment of 90 % irrigation water requirement (M_2I_2) through drip irrigation.

References

1. Alenazi M., H. Abdel-Razzak, A. Ibrahim, M. Wabih-Allah and A. Alsdon. 2015. Response of muskmelon cultivars to plastic mulch and irrigation regimes under greenhouse conditions. *J. Anim. Plant Sci.* 25(5):1398-1410.
2. Anisuzzaman, M., M.K. Uddin and M.A. Rahim. 2009. Planting time and mulching effect on onion development and seed production. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 8(3), pp. 412-416.
3. Anonymous. 2022. Indiastat Agri. <http://www.indiastatagri.com>.

4. **Dingre, S.D., D.D. Pawar and K.D. Kadam. 2012.** Productivity, water use and quality of onion seed production under different irrigation scheduling through drip. *Indian J. Agronomy* 57(2): 186-190.
5. **Enchalew B., Gebre S.L., Rabo M., Hindaye B., and A. Shafi. 2016.** Effect of deficit irrigation on water productivity of onion (*Allium cepa* L.) under drip irrigation. *Irrigation and Drainage Systems Engineering*. 5(3):1-4.
6. **Gupta, R.P. and Sharma, H.P. 2014.** Onion seed production: Scope, challenges and future strategy to meet the demand of quality seed. In: Brain storming Session on crop improvement and seed Production Onion, Organised at NHRDF, Nashik, 15th March, 2015, pp.1-12.
7. **Gupta R.A., D.K. Antala, J.V. Bhuvra and Geeta Tomar. 2013.** Effect of mulching on onion production. *A. Engg. Today*. 37(2):36-41.
8. **Gupta, R., Mishra K.P., and Hardaha M.K., 2017,** Response of garlic (*Allium sativaum* L.) cv. G-282 to different irrigation levels under drip irrigation system. *Int. J. App. Biosci.* 5 (6): 2320-7051.
9. **Mukul Kumar, Swipnil Dubey, P.K. Dwivedi, R.S. Rahav, L. Chakravarti and Mahitkumar. 2018.** Effect of different mulch on growth and yield of turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.). *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.* 9(1):1714-1719.
10. **Panase, V. G. and P. V. Sukhatme. 1967.** Statistical methods for Agricultural workers. New Delhi, ICAR.
11. **Parmar H.N., N.D. Polara, R.R. Viradiya. 2013.** Effect of mulching material on growth, yield and quality of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) Cv. Kiran. *Universal J. Agri. Res.* 1(2):30-37.
12. **Patle G.T., S.R. Yadav and Vanita Pandey. 2018.** Effect of irrigation levels and mulching on growth, yield and water use efficiency of cauliflower and broccoli in perhumid ecoregion. *Multilogic in Sci.* 8(25):188-191.
13. **Rubel M.H., Bobby F.B., Siddique A.B., Hossen K., and Sultana M.S. 2014.** Effect of mulching on seed production of onion. *Int. J. Sustain. Agril. Tech.* 10(11): 08-14.
14. **Sankar, V., A. Thangasamy and E. Lawande. 2015.** Effect of drip irrigation on onion seed production under western Maharashtra condition. *Inter. J. Tropical Agril.* 33(2): 621-625.
15. **Shahi V.S., L. Bhatt, S.K. Maurya and A.K. Singh. 2019.** Influence of different levels of drip irrigation and plastic mulching on yield, quality and economics of broccoli crop under Tarai region of Uttarakhand. *RASSA J. Sci. for Society.* 1(3):121-125.

Table.1 Effect of different mulches and drip irrigation levels on growth and seed yield parameter of onion

Treatments	Plant height (cm)	Height of primary flower stalk (cm)	Height of secondary flower stalk (cm)	Number of primary umbels per plant	Number of secondary umbels per plant	Diameter of primary umbel (cm)	Diameter of secondary umbel (cm)	Number of seed per primary umbel	Number of seed per secondary umbel	Seed yield per plant (g)	Seed yield per hectare (q)
Mulches (M)											
M ₁ – Organic Mulch	73.25	85.11	75.90	5.25	2.74	6.74	6.05	885.47	702.48	28.37	10.51
M ₂ – Polyethylene mulch	80.10	92.45	80.23	6.25	3.27	7.76	6.83	1057.72	785.50	32.69	12.11
M ₃ - No Mulch	65.84	77.44	71.49	3.88	1.79	5.70	4.69	735.66	626.48	22.34	8.64
'F' test	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE(m) ±	0.17	0.32	0.27	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.05	5.18	4.40	0.20	0.07
CD at 5%	0.57	0.96	0.83	0.06	0.13	0.09	0.16	15.55	13.20	0.65	0.23
Irrigation (I)											
I ₁ – 100 % (IWR)	74.90	87.03	77.39	5.45	2.83	7.06	6.18	939.91	735.39	29.26	10.84
I ₂ – 90 % (IWR)	73.40	85.30	75.87	5.15	2.58	6.77	5.82	899.15	709.38	28.81	10.67
I ₃ – 80 % (IWR)	70.90	82.68	74.36	4.79	2.38	6.37	5.57	839.79	669.69	26.33	9.75
'F' test	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE(m) ±	0.19	0.27	0.36	0.08	0.07	0.09	0.08	8.08	6.25	0.15	0.05
CD at 5%	0.61	0.82	1.10	0.25	0.23	0.29	0.26	24.24	18.75	0.47	0.17
Interaction (M X I)											
'F' test	Sig	Sig	Sig	NS	NS	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE(m) ±	0.21	0.25	0.14	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.06	3.85	4.24	0.17	0.07
CD at 5%	0.69	0.77	0.44	-	-	0.19	0.18	11.56	12.72	0.56	0.21

Table 2. Interaction effect of different mulches and irrigation levels on growth and seed yield parameter of onion

Treatments	Plant height (cm)	Height of primary flower stalk (cm)	Height of secondary flower stalk (cm)	Number of primary umbels per plant	Number of secondary umbels per plant	Diameter of primary umbel (cm)	Diameter of secondary umbel (cm)	Number of seed per primary umbel	Number of seed per secondary umbel	Seed yield per plant (g)	Seed yield per hectare (q)
M ₁ I ₁	75.27	87.57	77.27	5.61	2.98	7.03	6.30	942.69	721.64	29.19	10.81
M ₁ I ₂	73.39	84.94	75.62	5.21	2.71	6.72	6.03	892.32	709.51	28.87	10.69
M ₁ I ₃	71.09	82.83	74.82	4.92	2.52	6.47	5.82	821.41	676.29	27.06	10.02
M ₂ I ₁	82.18	94.58	81.77	6.43	3.41	8.13	7.12	1112.60	821.91	33.71	12.49
M ₂ I ₂	80.78	93.03	80.59	6.31	3.27	7.82	6.81	1063.87	786.31	33.19	12.29
M ₂ I ₃	77.35	89.74	78.33	6.02	3.12	7.32	6.57	996.68	748.27	31.16	11.54
M ₃ I ₁	67.25	78.93	73.12	4.30	2.11	6.02	5.12	764.43	662.63	24.89	9.22
M ₃ I ₂	66.02	77.92	71.41	3.92	1.75	5.78	4.62	741.26	632.31	24.37	9.03
M ₃ I ₃	64.25	75.46	69.93	3.43	1.51	5.31	4.33	701.28	584.51	20.76	7.69
'F' test	Sig	Sig	Sig	NS	NS	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig	Sig
SE(m) ±	0.21	0.25	0.14	0.06	0.08	0.06	0.06	3.85	4.24	0.17	0.07
CD at 5%	0.69	0.77	0.44	-	-	0.19	0.18	11.56	12.72	0.56	0.21